

High-Resolution real-Time Diagnostic Platform (realTPA) for Forest Fire and Landslide Early Warning

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Abstract: Climate change has intensified forest fires and landslides across mid-latitude regions. Conventional early warning systems rely mainly on meteorological data and lack spatial precision. This study presents the real-Time diagnostic Platform and Action system (realTPA), developed by the OJEong Resilience Institute at Korea University. realTPA delivers 100 m resolution risk mapping, processes multi-source data within one hour, and updates warnings every three hours. By integrating atmospheric variables with land surface indicators such as vegetation indices, topography, and fuel conditions, the system improves spatial specificity for disaster-prone areas. The forest fire model (CatBoost) achieved an AUC of 0.94, while the landslide model (Random Forest) reached an accuracy of 0.93 and AUC of 0.98. Operational validation over the Korean Peninsula (2025–2026) showed that 76% of 510 observed fire events occurred within 'Dangerous' or higher risk zones, and 89% of landslides fell in high or very high susceptibility classes. Case studies of the March 2025 Uiseong-gun fire and July 2024 Buyeo-gun landslide confirmed strong diagnostic reliability. Although technical performance is high, field utilization remains constrained by institutional barriers. realTPA offers a scalable framework for near real-time climate disaster early warning.

Keywords: forest fire; landslide; realTPA; early warning platform; disaster prevention industry.

1 Introduction

1.1 The new normal of climate disasters

Climate change is reshaping forest disasters by intensifying fire weather and rainfall-induced landslides in mountainous regions (Abatzoglou et al. 2019, Gariano and Guzzetti 2016). In South Korea, where forests cover about

63% of the territory, year-round fires and landslides are increasing under variable weather.

1.2 Limitations of conventional forecasting systems

Conventional systems rely mainly on AWS/ASOS observations and rainfall intensity-duration thresholds (Caine 1980, Guzzetti et al. 2008). Although the UNDRR (2016) framework emphasizes monitoring, risk assessment, communication, and preparedness, current administrative-scale warnings have three limitations:

- Spatial resolution: district-level forecasts cannot identify individual slopes, forest stands, or facilities at risk.
- Surface condition: ignition probability and slope failure vary with VTCl, vegetation structure, fuel load, and soil or terrain conditions even under similar weather.
- Operational linkage: response and recovery budgets still dominate, leaving limited capacity for prevention-oriented field action.

1.3 Research objectives

This study validates the realTPA (real-Time, Place and Action) platform through model performance assessment and operational case studies. It also outlines a prevention-oriented implementation framework that links real-time monitoring, place-specific diagnosis, and targeted action.

2 Data and system architecture

The realTPA platform features an automated pipeline for real-time collection, processing, and analysis of multi-source data. Figure 1 illustrates the overall data flow from meteorological and satellite data acquisition to the generation of location-based diagnostic results at 100 m resolution.

Figure 1. realTPA integrates meteorological, satellite, and anthropogenic data to produce 100 m resolution forest fire diagnostics.

2.1 Data sources and preprocessing

Data input into the platform is categorized into three groups:

- Meteorological data: temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and precipitation from ASOS and AWS stations.
- Remote sensing data: VTCI and NDVI from GK-2A/AMI and GEMS imagery to represent vegetation and surface dryness.
- Topographic and environmental data: 1:5,000 digital maps including slope, TRI, soil type, soil depth, and forest structure variables.

All data are standardized to a 100-meter grid through coordinate transformation and spatial resampling to ensure spatiotemporal consistency across all input layers.

2.2 Real-time processing pipeline

realTPA completes raw data acquisition to diagnostic map generation within one hour and updates outputs every three hours in line with KMA forecast cycles, enabling near real-time monitoring and short-term risk forecasting (Figure 2).

Figure 2. realTPA integrates meteorological and land surface data via AI to produce 100 m resolution diagnostic maps, updated hourly for forest fire and landslide services.

3 Materials and methods

3.1 Forest fire risk diagnosis: CatBoost-based model

Forest fire risk depends on weather and fuel conditions. Machine learning methods have shown strong wildfire-risk performance (Kang et al. 2020, Ruffault et al. 2018, Si et al. 2022). CatBoost was adopted for its handling of categorical and mixed geospatial variables (Roh et al. 2024).

Effective Humidity (EH), a key variable, represents cumulative drying effects on fuel flammability and is calculated by equation (1):

$$EH = (1 - r) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} r^n \cdot H_{t-n} \quad (1)$$

where r is the humidity dissipation coefficient (0.7) and H_{t-n} is the average relative humidity n days earlier. EH and satellite-derived VTCI estimate surface dryness, while population density and road proximity represent ignition risk.

Figure 3 compares conventional meteorological forecasting with realTPA's 100 m diagnostic approach integrating local surface conditions.

Figure 3. Comparison of conventional meteorological forecasting and realTPA's 100 m diagnostic approach: (a) Meteorological-based regional fire risk prediction, (b) Location-based diagnostic result integrating meteorological and surface data, showing improved spatial specificity.

3.2 Landslide susceptibility model: Random Forest

Landslide susceptibility is controlled by terrain and short-term rainfall. Random Forest was selected through PyCaret AutoML and hierarchical k-fold cross-validation because it often outperforms conventional statistical approaches (Reichenbach et al. 2018, Park and Kim 2019). The model provides 72-hour forecasts at 100 m resolution (Lee et al. 2025).

4 Results and validation

4.1 Algorithm performance metrics

Models were trained with 2016-2022 data and independently validated with 2023-2024 data using a 7:3 split. PyCaret AutoML selected CatBoost for fire and Random Forest for landslides. Both performed strongly, with landslide prediction (accuracy 0.93, AUC 0.98) exceeding forest fire prediction (accuracy 0.89, AUC 0.94) (Table 1).

4.2 Operational validation (2025-2026)

Operational reliability was assessed using 510 fire events from January 1, 2025 to March 15, 2026. Independent post-training validation is essential for real-world evaluation (Federici et al. 2015, Hakim et al. 2022). Table 2 summarizes events by risk category.

As shown in Table 2, 388 of 510 events (76%) were classified as 'Dangerous' or 'Very Dangerous' prior to occurrence, with the 2026 hit rate improving to 80% (166 of 207 events). These results demonstrate that realTPA provides operationally meaningful advance warning for the majority of observed forest fire events.

Table 1. Algorithm performance metrics for the forest fire and landslide diagnostic models.

Metric	Forest Fire (CatBoost)	Landslide (Random Forest)
Accuracy	0.89	0.93
Precision	0.87	0.95
Recall	0.88	0.92
AUC (ROC)	0.94	0.98
Kappa	0.81	0.85

Table 2. Distribution of 510 observed forest fire events across realTPA risk categories (Jan 2025 - Mar 2026).

Risk Category	Count	Ratio
Very Low	27	5.3%
Low	52	10.3%
Moderate	43	8.4%
Dangerous	263	51.5%
Very Dangerous	125	24.5%
Total	510	100%

4.3 Case study 1: Uiseong-gun forest fire, March 2025

On March 22, 2025, a major fire occurred in Uiseong-gun, Gyeongsangbuk-do at 11:00 AM. realTPA classified the area as Very Dangerous at 9:00 AM, two hours before ignition. Figure 4 overlays the 100 m diagnosis with the actual fire perimeter and ignition points (Figure 5), showing location-specific risk identification beyond broad regional forecasts.

4.4 Case study 2: Buyeo-gun landslide, July 2024

On July 10, 2024, concentrated rainfall affected Buyeo-gun, South Chungcheong Province. realTPA classified the area as Very High risk approximately 13 hours before reported landslides. Figure 6 presents the 100 m landslide risk map for the affected area, whereas Figure 7 presents detailed view of the ignition point.

Spatial analysis showed that over 95% of observed landslides occurred within grid cells classified as high or very high risk. This is consistent with 2023 validation results, where 96% of affected Tier 3 and Tier 4 regions were also identified as high hazard or above (Lee et al. 2025), confirming the model’s reliability for rainfall-induced landslide early warning.

Figure 4. Overlay of the realTPA 100 m resolution fire risk diagnosis with actual fire perimeters and ignition points for the March 2025 Uiseong-gun fire event.

Figure 5. Detailed view of ignition point 1 (Angye-myeon, Yanggok-ri, Uiseong-gun) showing the 100 m grid-level risk classification prior to the fire event.

Figure 6. Detailed map of overall landslide risk classification in Buyeo-gun.

Figure 7. Detailed view of the ignition point showing the 100 m grid-level risk classification prior to the landslide event.

5 Discussion

5.1 From forecasting to diagnosis: A paradigm shift

The results distinguish forecasting from diagnosis. Traditional systems estimate administrative-scale risk mainly from weather, whereas realTPA (Figure 8) combines weather with vegetation dryness, fuel load, slope, and human activity to identify high-risk locations.

5.2 The disaster prevention industry: Bridging technology and application

Figure 8. The realTPA web-based early warning platform (realTPA 2026), showing real-time forest fire risk visualization across the Korean Peninsula.

This study proposes a disaster prevention industrial ecosystem comprising:

- **Prevention Management Services:** Shifting fuel management (thinning, litter removal), species conversion, and drainage maintenance from one-off projects to ongoing services.
- **Local Job Creation:** Training residents in aging rural and mountainous areas as 'Climate Disaster Prevention Experts,' building regional development through disaster resilience.
- **Operational Infrastructure:** Digital twin-based systems that optimize patrol routes and provide real-time response guidance from diagnostic outputs.

5.3 Carbon neutrality and economic viability

Figure 4. Carbon emission and absorption changes before and after the March 2025 forest fire, showing carbon-neutral municipalities shifting to net emitters.

Disaster prevention also prevents carbon emissions (Figure 9). Protected forests can be valued as Avoided Emission Credits. Five carbon-neutral counties, including Uiseong-

gun, show 1.11 million tons of excess sequestration worth about 333 billion KRW, with broader social benefits from avoided recovery costs.

Linking Measurement, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) systems to carbon trading would let prevention activities generate quantifiable economic returns, advancing both climate neutrality and rural community development.

6 Conclusion

realTPA provides a reliable basis for proactive disaster management: validation classified 76-80% of observed events as high risk in advance, and case studies confirmed 2-13 hour lead times. Field action, however, requires operational infrastructure.

Disaster management should move from forecasting to diagnosis and from recovery to prevention, supported by a Disaster Prevention Industry that turns prevention into economic value.

A three-stage roadmap is proposed: (1) national realTPA deployment and prevention-focused local KPIs, (2) integration of avoided emission credits and a Disaster Prevention Industry special law within 3-5 years, and (3) a cross-ministerial platform with global standardization within 5-10 years. Prevention should be recognized as a strategic industry for climate adaptation, carbon neutrality, and regional equity.

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